

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-256-IG-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 256 250
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	279.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 279.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 10:08:07 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/7/2023 10:08:16 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.361	1766279	48.79	182426
2	6.773	1853785	51.21	153879

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-250-IG-5% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221014
Vial:	9	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 250
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	279.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 279.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2022 1:40:31 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 3:48:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.360	1925388	99.74	175812
2	6.740	5102	0.26	473